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SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL SURVEY OF ARACHNIDA

SANSA NEWSLETTER

NEW FORMAT FOR SANSA NEWS

The SANSA team decided to change the format of SANSA NEWS. We want to use the newsletter to publish information on new species records from South Africa as well as survey checklist results and new and interesting behavioral observations. This will be seen as a non-refereed publication and will therefore follow a more formal format to ensure that we can refer to the article. The following format should be followed where possible:

- Title
- Authors with addresses
- Abstract
- Keywords
- Introduction
- Materials and methods
- Results
- Conclusion
- References

However, we will still continue to report on interesting news, new taxonomic data, new student and other projects, congresses and other meetings.

A wealth of information is available and it needs to be published. If you have any information you would like to publish as a non-refereed paper, please contact me at DippenaarA@arc.agric.za.

NEXT INTERNATIONAL ARACHNOLOGICAL CONGRESS

The next meeting of the International Society of Arachnology will be held in Piriápolis (Maldonado, Uruguay) from March 6 to March 11, 2022. Uruguay is a peaceful and open-minded country located in the south east of South America, between Argentina and Brazil. The country has a long tradition in Arachnology, reflected by the large number of researchers working in various disciplines including taxonomy, systematics, ecology and animal behavior, using arachnids as model systems. They look forward to sharing their landscapes, culture and traditions with the Arachnological community!

Contact Anita Aisenberg the representation of the Organizing Committee of the 22nd International Congress of Arachnology in Uruguay.

Contact: 22ica.uy@gmail.com Instagram: @22ica22

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FEEDBACK ON THE 13 AFRAS COLLOQUIUM

Delegates at the 13th COLLOQUIUM

Delegates enjoying the Russian party

The 13th AFRAS colloquium, hosted by the University of Venda and the ARC, was held at Klein Kariba Resort in Limpopo, South Africa. This is the second time that a colloquium was hosted at Klein Kariba. During the meeting in 1996 the name of the Society was changed to AFRAS.

The objectives of these Colloquia are to promote research on the African Arachnida (non-Acari) and to provide a forum for the discussion of research on African arachnids in oral presentations, posters and workshops as well as informal discussions.

□ A total of 30 delegates attended the 13th colloquium from as far afield as Belgium, Canada, Germany, Russia, Czech Republic, Nigeria and Namibia.

□ 25 papers and six posters were presented during the colloquium.

□ Three workshops were held, "Southern African arachnid diversity" by Danilo Harms and two on Salticidae (keys and drawing) by Galina Azarkina.

AFRAS NEWS SNIPPETS

- Stefan Foord was reelected as the AFRAS chairman for the next three years.
- The next AFRAS colloquium will be organized by the ARC somewhere in Gauteng.
- To view the abstracts of colloquium visit the AFRAS website at <http://afras.ufs.ac.za>

POSTER AND PAPER AWARDS

Best presentation: **Tharina Bird**

Best student presentation: **Zingisile Mbo**

Best poster: **Milan Řezáč**

OTHER AFRAS AWARDS

Lawrence lifetime awards

Two Lawrence lifetime awards were handed out at the colloquium:

Dr Wanda Wesolowska received the Lawrence award for her dedication to African salticid spiders over the past 30 years.

Dr Gerbus Muller received the Lawrence award for his research on the medically important arachnids over the past 30 years.

Arina du Plessis handing Gerbus his award in Cape Town

Certificate of Merit for contributions for the period 2017-2020

Certificates of Merit were awarded to the South African Spider Red Listing Team for their contribution to African Arachnology for the period 2017-2020. Recipients were:

- Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman
- Charles Haddad
- Stefan Foord
- Robin Lyle
- Leon Lotz
- Theresa Sethusa and
- Domitilla Raimundo

Charles Haddad and Stefan Foord, two of the award recipients

Certificate of Merit

A Certificate of Merit was awarded to Peter Webb in recognition of his contribution to the African arachnological community. Peter is actively involved in surveys and photographing arachnids.

Stefan Foord handing Peter Webb his award

RED LIST OF SOUTH AFRICAN SPIDERS:
An end-product of the South African National Survey of Arachnida

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Charles Haddad², Stefan Foord³, Robin Lyle⁴, Leon Lotz⁵, Theresa Sethusa⁶, Domitilla Raimundo⁷

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INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) was launched in 1987 to improve knowledge of the arachnid diversity of the country through collaborative and co-ordinator research. During the last two decades considerable effort has been spent on collecting, identifying and describing the diverse arachnid fauna, and more products have been produced on the biodiversity of the country's arachnids, including the First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2015). This document included detailed information on the families, some records, conservation status of 2052 spider known from South Africa at the time.

Over time, significant resources have gone into identifying and describing species in preparation for the Spider Red Listing Project (SRLP), which will also include the species from Lesotho and Swaziland. This process is in the final stages, with an increased team made for each of the approximately 2000 species in 70 families now known from the region.

In July 2015, the Red Listing of spiders officially started with first workshop held in Pretoria. Team members of SANSA, under leadership of the Agricultural Research Council (ARC), along with the Threatened Species Programme (TSP) of the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI), have spent the past few months conducting the South African spider species specialist (SASS) survey. The SASS is a Red Listing of Threatened Species (RLTS) as a priority amongst the most comprehensive, objective global approach for evaluating the conservation status of past and animal species.

METHODS

Before Red Listing could be done, a large set of specimen information was required. Background information included:

- Common name
- Distribution: range, times known, records (individuals, illustrated or not, etc.)
- National status and relevant for this classification
- Level of endemism in some categories, as distribution globally and in South Africa (see Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2015)
- Habitat and ecology data
- Growth trends and general protection
- List of geographical localities from the three countries (Country, Province, Locality, Sublocality, National design or coordinates, with maps showing the distribution in the study area)
- Habitat images or photographs to illustrate appearance

RESULTS

To date, 2232 species of spiders have been recorded from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland combined. Six of these species are known only from Lesotho, as the number of species known from South Africa stands at 2225. The five most species-rich families from South Africa, all with 1100 spp. are: Lathisidae (550 spp.), Cribellariidae (171 spp.), Theridiidae (142 spp.), Lycosidae (111 spp.) and Araneidae (109 spp.). A total of 1382 spp. (62 %) are endemic to South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland, 17 % are endemic to southern Africa, 21 % are endemic to the biogeographic region, and approximately 4 % have a distribution extending beyond the biogeographic region.

Distribution records were largely concentrated around urban areas, and natural areas with high species diversity, particularly in the Blueberg and Orangeburg in the Limpopo Province, northern Free State, and the Cederberg and Cape Peninsula in the Western Cape (Fig. 1). The distribution of southern African endemics (Fig. 2) and South African endemics (Fig. 3) corresponds largely to the above, but information was clearly much higher in the southern third of the country (Western and Eastern Cape Provinces).

CONCLUSION

A Red List is far more than a mere record of species and their conservation status; it is also a tool to use to direct further research. The following information is now available:

- An updated National South African species list comprising of 2232 species is now available, of which 1104 are of least concern and 882 are data deficient.
- The Data Deficient species will be targeted. These are species whose range are not fully understood, described, known in type locality, are known from one or only a few specimens in any collection and/or whose range have been under sampled.
- Records of previous but possible invasive species.
- 68 species were found as threatened and need special attention.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., et al. 2010. First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). ARC - Research and Promotion, Pretoria, 1159 pp.

DIPPENAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., et al. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for determining spider diversity (Arachnida). *Transactions of Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245-275.

FIGURES 1-6: Maps of South Africa's nine provinces indicating (1) number of southern African endemics, (2) southern African endemics, and (3) South African endemics.

FIGURES 7-9: (7) Proportion of continental versus South African endemic species for the nine Red List boxes. (8) Number of endemic species per box. (9) Endemic species per box standardized by surface area.

FIGURES 10-11: (10) The largest proportion of spider species from any one family, while representing species in 6 families/provinces. Classification/Endemism/Endemism (relative) operational from many records (Fig. 11). This emphasizes the need for further sampling in large parts of South Africa to improve our knowledge of species' distributions.

FIGURES 12-14: (12) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (13) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 15-16: (15) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (16) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 17-18: (17) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (18) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 19-20: (19) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (20) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 21-22: (21) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (22) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 23-24: (23) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (24) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 25-26: (25) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (26) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 27-28: (27) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (28) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 29-30: (29) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (30) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 31-32: (31) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (32) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 33-34: (33) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (34) Number of southern African endemics.

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FIGURES 45-46: (45) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (46) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 47-48: (47) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (48) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 49-50: (49) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (50) Number of southern African endemics.

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FIGURES 89-90: (89) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (90) Number of southern African endemics.

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FIGURES 95-96: (95) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (96) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 97-98: (97) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (98) Number of southern African endemics.

FIGURES 99-100: (99) Number of spider species from South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland in each of the 10 Red List categories (standardized species) (100) Number of southern African endemics.

Poster presented at the Colloquium

**“Catch of the Day”
awarded to
Anka Eichhoff**

on 22 January 2020 at the 13th
Colloquium of the African
Arachnological Society

Stefan Foord
AFRAS Chairman

JANUARY 2020
Klein Kariba
South Africa

Anka Eichhoff

Anka collected a *Mysteria savanensis* at Makapansgat

Photo competition

A total of 70 photographs were submitted and Vida van der Walt put a presentation together of the images. There were different categories exhibited and especially the macro photographers blew us away with their beautiful photographs. There were three winners: Andrea Sander won three prizes, Bruce Blake one and Peter Webb one.

Best spider photograph - Andrea Sander

Best arachnid action photograph - Bruce Blake

Best non-spider photograph - Andrea Sander

Best arachnid photo story - Peter Webb

STUDENT PROJECTS

Exploring the impacts of famine weed (*Parthenium hysterophorus*) on spiders

Famine weed is one of the world's most serious weeds. It grows rapidly, produces large amounts of seeds, and displaces other plants species through the production of allelopathic compounds. Not only does this plant destroy grazing but the plant can poison livestock and impact on human health.

Thembeke Thwala from SANParks, currently registered as a MSc student at the University of Venda and Centre for Invasion Biology (Stellenbosch University) is exploring the impact of this weed on the wider ecosystem, focusing on nutrient cycling, soil properties and soil organisms. Fine scale responses of epigeal spiders to famine weed invasions were also investigated.

The study site was at Skukuza in the Kruger National Park. Famine weed has been recorded on the river banks of the Sabie and Crocodile River as well as disturbed sites in and around the Southern sections of the park. Pitfalls in a paired design that included invaded and uninvaded sites were used to compare sites.

Thembeke Thwala and Jarryd Foster at an invaded site near Skukuza (Kruger National Park)

Diversity and composition of spiders in three major habitats types of Phinda Private Game Reserve

There is a notable decline of biodiversity both local and globally. As a consequence, the conservation of natural spaces and species is of utmost importance and species checklists are a baseline for fulfilling these conservation plans. Spiders and ants are excellent taxa to act as surrogates to address issues concerning conservation. Spiders are the largest group of arachnids with more 48 000 described species world-wide.

Spiders are also sensitive to environmental changes and regulate prey populations; this allows for long term studies to monitor the health of the ecosystem in which they occur. This study aims to describe the diversity and distribution of ants and spiders in Phinda Private Game Reserve, which is a privately owned conservation reserve located in northern KwaZulu-Natal. This reserve has seven distinct habitats including the rare and critically endangered sand forest, which houses various rare endemic species.

Data collection was conducted in December 2018 (wet season) using pitfall traps. Three major habitats were sampled, namely savanna, sand-forest and sand-veld woodland.

The aim is to create a checklist and identify diversity patterns in these habitats. Identification of the spiders is still underway and no conclusions can be made at this time. This study forms part of the MSc project of Thandeka Mahlobo.

Project manager: Dr Caswell Munyai c2@ukzn.ac.za); Thandeka Mahlobo (thandekatee99@gmail.com)

Peter Webb

Salticidae *Stenaelurillus guttiger* one of the sp. sampled

STUDENT PROJECTS

Anthropogenic impacts on arthropod diversity along an arid elevational gradient

Mountains are considered as biodiversity hotspots because they can have variable environmental conditions within a limited spatial configuration. However, some of these mountains are under threat from climate change and especially from anthropogenic factors. Since land use changes have been shown to greatly influence biodiversity, the current study aims to investigate how the recent anthropogenic activities (changes in land-use) across the Soutpansberg Mountain have affected the epigeal arthropod diversity.

Ants and spiders were used as the model taxa because they are ideal biological indicators and also due to their higher diversity, sensitivity to environmental change and their role in the various ecosystem services they perform.

The study is a research project at the University of KwaZulu-Natal and has three objectives:

1. To determine how land use change and elevation affect ant and spider biodiversity
2. To determine whether the interaction between land use change and elevation affects ant and spider biodiversity
3. To determine the association of dominant taxa across the altitudinal transect in response to elevation, land use change and time (seasonal change)

A total of 18 sites were sampled across the mountain using pitfall traps. The sites were at different elevations (800 m a.s.l to 1700 m a.s.l), consisting of two aspects of the mountain and represent different land use types ranging from abandoned potatoes farm and blue-gum plantation, wildlife and cattle range and also macadamia orchards. The sampling took place in September 2019 while the next sampling is scheduled for early 2020.

Project manager: Caswell Munyai, Stefan Foord and MSc student Sphesihle Mkhungo (sphesihle07@gmail.com)

Peter Webb

Ammoxenidae *Ammoxenus amphalodes* a common sp. sampled

Effect of land use change on spider diversity in the communal areas of KwaZulu-Natal

Grassland ecosystems form the matrix for human livelihoods and are therefore threatened by human population growth, transformations and land use change. The extent of utilization threatens their sustainability and determines whether the ecosystem will be resilient to natural and human disturbance, or will result in degradation and/or invasions by other undesirable species. The current study aims to understand the response of biodiversity to various land use regimes in communal areas located in the grassland biome by assessing the taxonomic and functional diversity of ants, spiders, grasses and forbs. Specifically, it determines the impact of human settlements, croplands and rangelands on taxonomic, functional and beta diversity.

Species richness, composition, abundance and distribution, as well as the variations in response of spider diversity to land use pattern and the interactions between the species diversity and their drivers are also investigated. Spiders were collected using pitfall traps between November and April of 2018 from nine communal areas (along a density gradient) across the grasslands and in two relatively pristine/ untransformed grasslands for comparison in KwaZulu-Natal.

Project manager; Dr Caswell Munyai (Munyaic2@ukzn.ac.za) and PhD student Ms Concilia Mukanga (cmukanga@gmail.com)

Female *Latrodectus umbukwane* with egg sac. Photo from Wright et al 2019

A new button spider species, *Latrodectus umbukwane*, was newly described from Phinda Game Reserve in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa.

Wright et al. (2019) provide ecological, behavioural and developmental notes on the species as well as a phylogeny based on mitochondrial cytochrome-oxidase I (COI) to support proposed relationships.

They also provided an updated key to the southern African species, and data that may be used to recognize this species.

REFERENCE

Wright, B. M. O. G., Wright, C. D., Sole, C. L., Lyle, R., Tippett, R., Sholto-Douglas, C., Verburgt, L. & Engelbrecht, I. (2019). A new forest dwelling button spider from South Africa (Araneae, Therididae, *Latrodectus*). *Zootaxa* 4700(4): 584-600. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.4700.4.12

MORE ON CLADOMELEA

The first records of the bolas spider, *Cladomelea longipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) was reported by Dippenaar-Schoeman and Foord (2019), resulting in a considerable extension of its geographic range in Africa. *Cladomelea longipes* is very rare locally but has a relatively large geographical distribution in the Afrotropical Region. *C. longipes* was compared with the two other species of *Cladomelea* known from South Africa, *C. akermani* Hewitt, 1923 and *C. debeeri* Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004. Images of live specimens and a distribution map are provided.

Cladomelea longipes

Figure 1. Afrotropical distribution of *Cladomelea* species known from South Africa: *C. longipes* (blue squares), *C. akermani* (green triangle) and *C. debeeri* (red circle).

C. akermani photo: John Roff

C. debeeri photo John Roff

C. longipes Meg Cumming

REFERENCE

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A. S. & Foord, S. H. (2019). New records of *Cladomelea* from South Africa, including the first records of *C. longipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) (Araneae, Araneidae) outside its type locality. *Check List* 15(6): 1071-1075.

TAXONOMIC CHANGES

In a paper by Nentwig *et al.* (2019) they undertook an in depth study of the species described by Strand, and according to them Strand considered each deviation of specimens from the original description in colouration, body size and shape, eye pattern or leg spination as sufficient to describe infraspecific taxa such as subspecies, varieties, forms and aberrations. Following this problematic approach, he erected 165 infraspecific names which may reflect phenetics rather than evolutionary history. The aim of their new paper was to review the 102 still valid names according to current taxonomic standards.

THOMISIDAE

Camaricus nigrotesselatus lineitarsus Strand, 1907 = **nomen dubium**

Following Strand (1907: 651) this variety from South Africa is, based on one male and one female, characterized by a larger black dorsal line on the metatarsi which, in contrast to the nominate form (distributed in Central, East and Southern Africa), reaches the tarsi. Bonnet (1956: 941) synonymized it with the nominate form but the World Spider Catalog (2019) lists it as a subspecies. The type material belonged to the museum Lübeck that was completely destroyed during the Second World War. In addition, they were also unable to find the type material in any of the other contacted museums, so it has to be assumed that it is lost. They conclude that *Camaricus nigrotesselatus lineitarsus* Strand, 1907 is a nomen dubium.

Synema imitatrix meridionale Strand, 1907 = nomen dubium *Synema imitator* (Pavesi, 1883) = ***Synema imitatrix* (Pavesi, 1883), correction**

Due to differences in colouration and slight differences in body size and leg length, Strand (1907: 600) described this female variety from South Africa. Bonnet (1958: 4203) synonymized it with the nominate form and the World Spider Catalog (2019) lists it as a subspecies. The nominate form *Synema imitatrix* (Pavesi, 1883) has been described from Ethiopia, but is also known from South Africa. Pavesi's original ending imitator was incorrectly changed by Dahl (1907: 382) from the feminine imitatrix to imitator. According to the CODE (ICZN 2012) this is not correct, since only an "adjectival or participial species-group name must agree in gender with the generic name", whereas a noun in apposition must not be changed; imitatrix is a noun ("female imitator") and not an adjective. Therefore the correct name of the nominate form is *Synema imitatrix* (Pavesi, 1883). They could not detect the type material in any of the contacted museums, it belonged to the museum Tübingen and is probably lost. So we consider Strand's taxon as a nomen dubium.

REFERENCES

- Bonnet P 1956 Bibliographia araneorum. Douladoure, Toulouse. Vol. 2(2): 919-1926.
- Bonnet P 1958 Bibliographia araneorum. Douladoure, Toulouse. Vol.2(4): 3027-4230
- Strand E 1907h Afrikanische Spinnen (exkl. Aviculariiden) hauptsächlich aus dem Kapland. – Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Geographie und Biologie der Tiere 25: 557-731

They declared 39 subspecies as new synonyms of the nominate form, and they confirm 10 previously overlooked synonymies of subspecies with the nominate form, and 26 taxa are nomina dubia (some described from juveniles or type material destroyed afterwards). In 24 cases they recommend in-depth taxonomic studies on subspecies and species complexes (subspecies and species inquirenda).

Two cases dealt with South African thomisid species.

REFERENCE

- Nentwig, W., Blick, T., Gloor, D., Jäger, P. & Kropf, C. (2019). Tackling taxonomic redundancy in spiders: the infraspecific spider taxa described by Embrink Strand (Arachnida: Araneae). *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* 58: 29-51. doi:10.30963/aramit5809

Peter Webb

Valid species: *Camaricus nigrotesselatus* female

Martie Rheeder

Camaricus nigrotesselatus male

John Richter

Valid species: *Synema imitatrix* female(above)

Peter Webb

TAXONOMIC CHANGES

TWO NEW TETRAGNATHA SYNONYMS

The long-jawed spider genus *Tetragnatha* Latreille, 1804 (family Tetragnathidae) comprises 349 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). From South Africa 12 species have been reported based mainly on the paper by Okuma & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1988).

Several *Tetragnatha* species have wide distribution patterns. In a new paper by Castanheira *et al.* (2019) they analyse most of the widespread species of *Tetragnatha* mainly in the Neotropical region. In this paper two of the species reported from South Africa were synonymized. They are:

- *Tetragnatha boydi* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1898 = *Tetragnatha bogotensis* Keyserling, 1865 (Castanheira *et al.*, 2019b: 467).
- *Tetragnatha maxillosa* Thorell, 1895 = *Tetragnatha keyserlingi* Simon, 1890 (Castanheira *et al.*, 2019b: 477).

REFERENCES

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OKUMA, C. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A. S. (1988). *Tetragnatha* (Araneae: Tetragnathidae) in the collection of the Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria with a description of a new species. *Phytophylactica* 20: 219-232.

Tetragnatha nitens

SA Species in World Spider Catalog

The World Spider Catalogue (WSC) is online available and is the most important document for spider taxonomists. The WSC is a powerful tool that is lacking for most other invertebrate groups. Data is captured almost on a daily basis mainly from taxonomic papers. The species distribution record provided for each species are mainly extracted from these taxonomic papers. Unfortunately data from ecology, ethology, and physiology research papers are not included in the WSC.

Many arachnologists uncritically rely on this supplementary distribution and for many countries the species diversity is under reported. This is also true for South Africa where 332 species listed on the South African National species list are not captured in the WSC. This includes frequently very common species such as for example *Leucauge decorata* (Blackwall, 1864). Also for many species only "Africa" is listed without any reference to exact country localities.

To overcome this problem several of the South African taxonomists are going to try to provide more taxonomic data on South African species. A first example is the Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019) article on the *Cladomelea* species.

More information is now available on South African species such as distribution patterns, lifestyle and behaviour with images of live specimens. It is important that this information is published. In future, more species data will be published as part of SANSA news. For the first article on *Araneus coccinella* see page 12

WRONG SPECIES

In several books and papers we have wrongly identified the spider on photo (Fig. 1) as the araneid, *Araneus coccinella*. However after recent new photographs obtained from Peter Webb we discovered the true *Araneus coccinella* (Fig. 2). See article p.12

Fig. 1.

Genus undetermined? Photo Les Oates

Fig. 2

Araneus coccinella. Photo Peter Webb

SURVEY DATA

BIOSPHERE RESERVES

UNESCO's Man and the Biosphere programme addresses the impact of man on the environment by studying the social, ecological and economic implications of biodiversity loss. It then takes steps to minimize this loss through sharing of knowledge, research and monitoring, education and training, and multilateral decision-making.

Biosphere reserves are nominated by governments for inclusion in the Man and the Biosphere programme. Whether they are terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine in nature, all are experimental areas where different approaches to integrated environmental management are tested. This is important as it helps to deepen our knowledge of what works in conservation and sustainable development.

South Africa initiated its participation in the UNESCO Biosphere Reserve Programme in 1995 during the Second World Congress of Biosphere Reserves in Spain, and entered into a Memorandum of Understanding with UNESCO in April 1998. See list of South African BR (Table 1 and Fig 1)

TABLE 1 South African Biosphere Reserves

BIOSPHERE RESERVE	PROVINCE	YEAR DESIGNATED	SIZE (ha)
Kogelberg	Western Cape	1900	100 000
Cape West Coast	Western Cape	2000	378 000
Waterberg	Limpopo	2001	417 000
Kruger to Canyon	Limpopo and Mpumalanga	2001	2 474 700
Cape Wine-lands	Western Cape	2007	322 000
Vhembe	Limpopo	2009	3 070 000
Gouritz Cluster	Eastern and Western Cape	2015	3 187 893
Magaliesberg	Gauteng and North West	2015	357 870
Garden Route	Western and Eastern Cape	2017	698 363
Marico	North West	2018	447 269

FOR DETAILED INFORMATION VISIT THE FOLLOWING WEBSITE

The Biosphere Reserve Programme in South Africa is managed by the Department of Environmental Affairs (DEA). For more information see

- https://www.environment.gov.za/sites/default/files/reports/southafricanstrategy_biospherereserve2016_2020.pdf
- <http://online.fliphtml5.com/koew/undf/#p=1>

Fig. 1. South African Biosphere Reserves

SANSA SURVEYS IN BIOSPHERE RESERVES

With the extensive SANSA surveys undertaken data is now available for most of the Biosphere Reserves (BR).

Most of the BR now have websites with information. The first BR that SANSA has provided information for is the Waterberg Biosphere Reserve. This information can be viewed at <http://www.waterberg-bioquest.co.za/>

A total of **502 species** of spiders have to date (2020) been recorded from this area. A spreadsheet of all the species can be downloaded from the website. The species that have been photographed in the Waterberg can be viewed by clicking on the species name.

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RECENT PUBLICATIONS

CASTANHEIRA, P. DE S., BAPTISTA, R. L. C., PIZZETTI, D. D. P. & TEIXEIRA, R. A. 2019. Contributions to the taxonomy of the long-jawed orb-weaving spider genus *Tetragnatha* (Araneae, Tetragnathidae) in the Neotropical region, with comments on the morphology of the chelicerae. *Zoosystematics and Evolution* 95(2): 465-505. doi:10.3897/zse.95.36762.

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First records for the orb-web spider *Arachnura scorpionoides* Vinson, 1863 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Abstract

The scorpion tail orb-web spider *Arachnura scorpionoides* Vinson, 1863 is for the first time reported from South Africa. This species has been recorded throughout South Africa, extending its current distribution range in Africa from Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Seychelles, Mayotte, Madagascar, Mauritius and Réunion to South Africa. The general morphology of the species is described. Life photographs are provided with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation.

Key words: conservation, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Arachnura* of the family Araneidae is known as the tailed spider or scorpion tail spider (Arachne-spider and nura-tail). The genus was described by Vinson (1863) with *Arachnura scorpionoides* as the type species. The genus is represented by 12 species and has a wide distribution known from India, China, Africa and Australia (World Spider Catalogue 2020).

Arachnura scorpionoides is the only species known Africa and has so far been reported from the Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Seychelles, Mayotte, Madagascar, Mauritius and Réunion. The male is still unknown. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) large numbers of specimens were sampled and became available for research (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). Between the sampled material the scorpion tail orb-web spider *A. scorpionoides* has been identified. This paper reports on the morphological variation observed, their behaviour and occurrence in South Africa.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) requests were made for photographs of species for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012). Several sets of photographs of *A. scorpionoides* have been received from the public. Photographs in laboratory taken by a Leica V3.6.0 system. The new records reported on here are from specimens collected during SANSA surveys. The voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division.

TAXONOMY

Arachnura scorpionoides Vinson, 1863

Arachnura scorpionoides Vinson, 1863: 291, 310, pl. 13, f. 1 (Df).

Hapalochrota caudata Keyserling, 1864: 82, pl. 3, f. 6-11 (Df).

Arachnura scorpionoides Uyemura, 1976b: 26, f. 1.2, 4, 6, 2.1-2, 3.1, 4.1 (f).

Arachnura scorpionoides Saaristo, 2010: 33, f. 4.1-2 (f); Cazanove & Begue, 2018: 22; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014.

Figure 1a-b *Arachnura scorpionoides* female from Kruger National Park (a) lateral view (b) dorsal view Photo credit Vida van der Walt

Diagnostic characters: Size: females TL 7–10 mm. This species is very distinct in the tail like shape of the abdomen (Fig. 1a). Cephalothorax broad, narrowing anteriorly. In alcohol material dark markings visible medially and around border (Fig. 2a). Eyes in two rows with posterior median eyes closely spaced, median ocular area longer than wide (Fig. 2a); lateral eyes closely spaced on lateral border. Abdomen broad with two horn like projections protruding over the cephalothorax in a V-shape; it then tapers into a long tail with soft lobes on the tips (Fig. 3c). The front legs are stronger than the rest and kept close to the body when alive. Some change in colour was observed as the seasons change (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) specimens are more yellow in summer (Fig. 2a) and becoming duller brown in winter (Figs 2b,2c). In a recent paper by Cazanove & Begue (2018) they observed similar colour variations in *A. scorpionoides* from Réunion. They reported on a yellow, fawn and brown form.

Figure 2a-b. (a) *Arachnura scorpionoides* female carapace dorsal view; (b) female epigynum.

Figure 3a–d. *Arachnura scorpionoides* female (a) female yellow photograph Gawie le Roux ; (b) brown form female hanging in web photograph Karen Fourie; (c) female lateral view showing soft lobes at the tip photo Andrea Sanders

BEHAVIOUR

Arachnura scorpionoides construct a permanent but incomplete orb-web with an open hub. The web is suspended on an angle and has a V-shaped section missing from the top of the web. In autumn/winter, the female produces a series of woolly brownish egg sacs which she strings together in a line from the centre of the web to fill the missing section. The spider took up position at the bottom of the string in the centre of the web (Figs 4a,4b.) The female spider can curl her tail up over her back like a scorpion if she is disturbed (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009).

Figure 4a–b. *Arachnura scorpionoides* female (a) female in web below egg sacs photo Roelien Dreyer; (b) female hanging in web photograph photo Cynthia le Roux.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Seychelles, Mayotte, Madagascar, Mauritius, Réunion. News records: South Africa

MATERIAL EXAMINED

SOUTH AFRICA. *Eastern Cape:* Port Elizabeth (-33.95 S; 25.61 E), F. Schultz leg., 1.ii.1974, 1 imm. (NCA 76/250). *KwaZulu-Natal:* iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay Park (-27.92 S, 32.27 E), L. Prendini leg., 5.i.1989, 1 f (NCA 89/525); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Fanie's Island (-28.10 S, 32.45 E), M. Filmer leg., 23.vii.1990, imm f (NCA 90/245); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63 S, 32.25 E), M. Filmer leg. 22.vii.1990, 1 f (NCA 90/224);

iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40 S, 32.6 E), M. Filmer leg, 14.x.1990, 1 f (NCA 91/689); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87 S, 32.24 E), C. Haddad leg, 3.iv.2004, 1f (NCA 2004/1223); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72 S, 32.38 3), S. Lovell leg., 5.iii.1989, 1f (NCA 2004/678); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27 S, 30.57 E), R. Maartens leg., 25.iii.1986, 1f (NCA 86/582). *Limpopo:* Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45), A. Fischer leg. 3.ii.2005, 1f (NCA 2006/1036); *Mpumalanga:* Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00), A. Leroy leg., 10.iii.2007, 1f (NCA 2008/2949); Pilgrims Rest (- 24.89, 30.75), M. Filmer leg., 29.xii.1988, 1f (NCA 90/67); Schagen (- 25.43, 30.80), M.vd Berg leg., 19.viii.1997, tree fogging, 1f (NCA 98/184). *North West:* Brits (-25.62, 27.77) , M. Filmer leg., 28.ii.1989, 1f (NCA 89/584). *Western Cape:* Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48), N. Larsen leg., 15.ii.2010, 1f (NCA 2010/623).

SANSA VM Photo gallery; Tsitsikamma National Park (- 33.98 S, 23.52 E), Gawie Le Roux leg. 1f (VM SANSA 2010/107); Stilbaai (-34.36, 21.43) Geldenhuys Koos SANSA 2008/389 , Bellville K. Marais, VM SANSA 2010/342; Port Elizabeth (Le Roux Willie & Cynthia) VM SANSA 2009/508 Kruger National Park Vida vd Walt VM SANSA 2009/405.

Fig. 5. Map showing the distribution of *Arachnura scorpionoides* in South Africa

HABITAT

The species was sampled in the Fynbos, Savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled in macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2001) during tree fogging. In the Ndumo Game Reserve the species was sampled from the Broadleaf woodland; Ficus forest riparian forests along Pongola and Usutu rivers and Subtropical bush (Haddad *et al.* 2006)

CONSERVATION

An African endemic recorded from six African countries. In South Africa, it is known from six provinces and >10 protected areas (Fig. 5). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

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